

Ishtar's Descent to the Underworld

By Louise Pryke, University of Sydney

Entry tags: Sumerian Text, Ancient Mesopotamian Text, Mesopotamian Religions, Religious Group, Text

Ishtar's Descent to the Netherworld is perhaps the most famous myth about the Mesopotamian goddess of love, war, and social connections, Ishtar. Ishtar's Descent is known from its Sumerian and Akkadian versions, with the Sumerian considered to be the earlier text. Although there is some variation between the two texts, the main narrative is relatively consistent in the earlier and later versions. The narrative describes the journey of Ishtar to the Mesopotamian underworld, the domain of her sister, Ereshkigal. Ishtar is killed in the underworld, and Ea (wisdom deity) must find a way to revive her - as all earthly fertility has ceased. Finally, Ishtar is released from the Netherworld, but must provide a substitute in her place. Ishtar's connection to death is an area where modern understanding is limited, yet her own experience of death is uniquely connected to her transgressive nature, seen in her broader image. Ishtar's ability, demonstrated in myth, to visit the underworld and then to return to the land of the living, is a powerful manifestation of her supernatural qualities. Inanna's unique expertise in entering and escaping the underworld is likely to be a leading cause for her association with death, the afterlife, and the voyage in between. Iconographic evidence, such as the Burney Relief, appear to reflect the goddess' associations with death, and the myth of the Descent may also be connected to the deity's role in healing. Ishtar's healing ability is a prominent aspect of her close relationship with the Mesopotamian king. Among many blessings, she is said in hymns to give the king "life." Although the granting of "life" is a complex blessing, several texts reference the goddess' ability to add years to a lifespan, with the implied benefit of forestalling death. At other times, she is credited with the power to bring the dead back to life. Like other significant works of cuneiform literature, such as The Epic of Gilgamesh, Ishtar's Descent was lost from general cultural awareness along with the cuneiform script, which disappeared around the 1st century CE. The recovery of cuneiform in the late 18th century allowed for the reintroduction of the ancient myth, and its divine protagonist, to modern audiences.

Date Range: 1000 BCE - 600 BCE

Region: Ancient Mesopotamia

Region tags: Syria, Iraq

A rough map of the ancient Near Eastern region of Mesopotamia.

Status of Readership:

✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists

Sources and Corpora

Print Sources

Print sources used for understanding this subject:

- Source 1: Foster, Benjamin R. *Before the Muses: an Anthology of Akkadian Literature*. 3rd ed. Bethesda, Md: CDL Press, 2005.
- Source 2: Barrett, Caitlín. "Was Dust Their Food and Clay Their Bread? Grave Goods, the Mesopotamian Afterlife, and the Liminal Role of Inana/Ishtar." *Journal of Ancient Near Eastern Religions* 7, no. 1 (2007): 7-65. <https://doi.org/10.1163/156921207781375123>.

Reference: Mander, Pietro. Ishtar La Stella. La via Della Conoscenza E L'unione Degli Opposti Nei Sumeri E Assiro-babilonesi. Ester, 2022. <https://www.libroco.it/english/dl/Pietro-Mander/Ester/9788899668617/Ishtar-la-stella-La-Via-della-Conoscenza-e-l-unione-degli-Opposti-nei-Sumeri-e-Assiro-Babilonesi/cw903623885102358.html>.

Reference: Pryke, Louise M.. Ishtar. Taylor & Francis, 2017. <https://play.google.com/store/books/details?id=fggqDwAAQBAJ>.

Online Sources

Online sources used for understanding this subject:

- Source 1 URL: <https://www.worldhistory.org/ishtar/>
- Source 1 Description: An accessible introduction to the goddess Ishtar, primary character in the Descent.
- Source 2 URL: https://www.britishmuseum.org/collection/object/W_K-162
- Source 2 Description: Image of the 7th century BCE clay tablet with Ishtar's Descent inscribed.

Online Corpora

Relevant online Primary Textual Corpora (original languages and/or translations)

- Source 1 URL: https://cdli.ox.ac.uk/wiki/doku.php?id=descent_ishtar_netherworld
- Source 1 Description: Entry on Ishtar's Descent. Courtesy of "Ishtar's Descent to the Netherworld," CDLI: The Cuneiform Digital Library Initiative, last modified 2017.
- Source 2 URL: <https://etcsl.orinst.ox.ac.uk/section1/tr141.htm>
- Source 2 Description: Text translation of Inanna's Descent to the Underworld, the Sumerian version, for contrast. Courtesy of Black, J.A., Cunningham, G., Fluckiger-Hawker, E, Robson, E., and Zólyomi, G., The Electronic Text Corpus of Sumerian Literature (<http://www-etcsl.orient.ox.ac.uk/>), Oxford 1998- .

General Variables

Is the text stored in a specific location?

[Note at which point in time, for reference, if known; select all that apply]

– Yes

Notes: There was a copy of the text in the Great Library of Ashurbanipal. It is unknown where the text may have also resided.

Tomb

– Field doesn't know

Cemetery

– Field doesn't know

Temple

– Field doesn't know

↳ Shrine

– Field doesn't know

↳ Altar

– Field doesn't know

↳ Devotional marker

– Field doesn't know

↳ Cenotaph

– No

↳ Church

– No

↳ Mosque

– No

↳ Synagogue

– No

↳ Triumphal Arch

– No

↳ Monument

– Field doesn't know

↳ Mass Gathering Point

– No

↳ Cave(s)

– No

↳ Hilltops

– No

↳ Other natural sanctuaries

– No

↳ Boundary markers or lines

– No

↳ Domestic contexts

– No

↳ Library/archive

– Yes

↳ Specify

–Specify: The Library of Ashurbanipal

Methods of Composition

– Impressed

↳ Tool for making the impression(s)

–Other [specify]: Stylus

Medium upon which the text is written/incised

– Clay

↳ Clay object

– Clay tablet

↳ Type of clay

–Type of clay: Wet clay

Is the location where the text stored accompanied by iconography or images?

– No

Was the material modified before the writing or incising process?

– Physical preparation

Is the area where the text is stored accompanied by an-iconic images?

– No

Was the text modified before the writing or incising process?

– Other [specify]: Probably modified through oral retelling

Materiality

Methods of Composition

– Impressed

Tool for making the impression(s)

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- ↳ Synagogue
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- ↳ Triumphal Arch
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– Yes

↳ Specify

– Specify: The Library of Ashurbanipal

Is the location where the text stored accompanied by iconography or images?

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Is the area where the text is stored accompanied by an-iconic images?

– No

Production & Intended Audience

Is the production of the text funded by the polity?

– Yes

|

- ↳ Are the authors/copyists/engravers paid by the polity?
 - Field doesn't know

- ↳ Does the polity provide financial support to religious infrastructure involved with textual production?
 - Yes

- ↳ Are the leaders of the polity and the religion the same figure?
 - Yes

- ↳ Are political officials involved in the support of textual production?
 - Yes

- ↳ Are political officials and religious officials otherwise overlapping institutional networks?
 - Yes

- ↳ Does the polity enforce religious observance according to text or texts?
 - I don't know

- ↳ Is the polity legal code derived from religious text(s) in question?
 - Field doesn't know

- ↳ Is preferential economic treatment (e.g. tax exemption) present in the polity to support the text(s)...
 - Field doesn't know

- ↳ Are religious specialists present/in charge of the production of the text or copies of the text?
 - Yes
 - ↳ Present full-time?
 - Field doesn't know

 - ↳ Present part-time?
 - Field doesn't know

 - ↳ Are the religious specialists of a specific sex/gender?

– No

↳ Are the religious specialists of a specific ethnicity?

– Field doesn't know

↳ Are the religious specialists of a specific class/caste?

– Yes

↳ Is this class/caste based on a cultural status?

– Yes

↳ Is this class/caste based on socioeconomic status?

– Field doesn't know

↳ Are the religious specialists dedicated to the place for life?

– Field doesn't know

↳ Are the religious specialists stratified in a hierarchical system?

– Yes

↳ Is access within the space segregated by this hierarchy?

– Field doesn't know

↳ Are there regulations/provisions for living spaces of religious specialists?

– Yes

↳ Are there regulations/provisions for training spaces of religious specialists?

– Yes

↳ Are there formal institutions for the maintenance of a body of religious specialists?

– Yes

What is the estimated number of people considered to be the audience of the text

This should be the total number of people who would serve as the intended audience for the text.

– Field doesn't know

Does the Religious group actively proselytize and recruit new members?

– Field doesn't know

Is the text considered official religious scripture?

– Field doesn't know

Written in distinctly religious/sacred language?

– Field doesn't know

Are there clear reformist movements?

(Reformism, as in not proselytizing to potential new conservative, but "conversion" - or rather, reform - to the "correct interpretation"?)

– No

Is the text in question employed in ritual practice?

– Field doesn't know

Is there material significance to the text?

– Field doesn't know

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(Reformism, as in not proselytizing to potential new conservative, but "conversion" - or rather, reform - to the "correct interpretation"?)

– No

Is the text in question employed in ritual practice?

– Field doesn't know

Is there material significance to the text?

– Field doesn't know

Context and Content of the Text (Beliefs and Practices)

Is a spirit-body distinction present in the text?

– I don't know

Is supernatural monitoring present in the text?

– No

Is the text - or does the text include - a ritual list, manual, bibliography, index, or vocabulary?
(Select all that apply)

– Other [specify]: No

Does the text require celibacy (full sexual abstinence)?

– No

Are general social norms prescribed by the text?

– Yes

Are messianic beliefs present in the text?

– No

Is the text itself accompanied by art?

– No

Notes: No, although it has been argued persuasively that the Burney Relief reflects Ishtar in the narrative.

Are there lineages or a single lineage established by the text?

– No

Is belief in an afterlife indicated in the text?

– Yes

↳ Is the spatial location of the afterlife specified or described by the religious group?

– Yes

↳ Afterlife in specified realm of space beyond this world?

– Yes

↳ Afterlife in vaguely defined "above" space?

– No

↳ Afterlife in vaguely defined "below" space?

– Yes

↳ Afterlife in "other" space?

– Yes

↳ Is the temporality of the afterlife specified or described by the religious group?

– No

↳ Is there debate in the interpretation of the language of the afterlife?

– Yes

↳ What are the historically mainstream positions in the debate?

–Specify: There is some debate about where the entrance to the Underworld may be located

↳ What are the historically minority positions?

–Specify: See above debate on entrance to the Underworld.

Does the text require constraints on sexual activity (partial sexual abstinence)?

– No

Notes: No, but Ishtar's death results in the temporary cessation of all earthly fertility, causing a cosmic crisis.

Is there a conventional vs. moral distinction in the religious text?

– No

Is an eschatology present in the text?

– No

Do supernatural beings mete out punishment in the text?

– No

Notes: Yes but not to humans

Are there multiple versions of the text?

– Yes

Notes: There is an earlier Sumerian version which is longer and more detailed, along with the manuscripts from Ashurbanipal's Library and Assur.

↳ Are multiple versions viewed as proper?

– Yes

↳ If multiple versions are proper, is there a differentiation among versions by any means?

– Yes

Notes: The Sumerian version is perhaps the original and longer and more detailed. It also gives details on Ishtar's relationship with her assistant, Ninshubur, which are missing from the later version.

↳ Age of extant version of text?

– Yes

↳ Content of text?

– Yes

Notes: The text of Ishtar's Descent is incomplete.

↳ Ritual purpose of text?

– No

↳ Is there debate about which version is proper?

– No

Notes: Both versions are considered to reflect variations of the story.

Does the text require castration?

– No

Does the text express a formal legal code?

– No

Is belief in reincarnation in this world specified in the text?

– Yes

↳ In human form?

– No

↳ In animal/plant form?

– No

↳ In form of an inanimate object(s)?

– No

↳ In non-individual form (i.e. some form of corporate rebirth, tribe, lineage, etc.)?

– No

↳ Reincarnation linked to notion of life-transcending causality (e.g. karma)?

– Yes

↳ Other form of reincarnation in this world?

– Yes

↳ In textual exegesis among practitioners are there debates about reincarnation?

– No

Is the text part of a collection of texts?

– Field doesn't know

Notes: There are related stories, such as the courtship of Inanna and Dumuzi, but it is unclear how it all fits together.

Do supernatural beings bestow rewards in the text?

– No

Notes: Yes but not to humans. Ishtar rewards her faithful followers in the Sumerian version.

Are there centrally important virtues advocated by the text?

– Yes

↳ Honesty/trustworthiness/integrity
– Yes

↳ Courage (in battle)
– No

↳ Courage (generic)
– Yes

↳ Compassion/empathy/kindness/benevolence
– Yes

↳ Mercy/forgiveness/tolerance
– Yes

↳ Generosity/charity
– No

↳ Selflessness/selfless giving
– Yes

↳ Righteousness/moral rectitude
– Yes

↳ Ritual purity/ritual adherence/abstention from sources of impurity
– Yes

↳ Respectfulness/courtesy
– Yes

↳ Familial obedience/filial piety

– Yes

↳ Fidelity/loyalty

– Yes

Notes: Big yes.

↳ Cooperation

– Yes

↳ Independence/creativity/freedom

– Yes

↳ Moderation/frugality

– No

↳ Forbearance/fortitude/patience

– No

↳ Diligence/self-discipline/excellence

– Yes

↳ Assertiveness/decisiveness/confidence/initiative

– Yes

↳ Strength (physical)

– No

↳ Power/status/nobility

– Yes

↳ Humility/modesty

– Yes

↳ Contentment/serenity/equanimity

– No

↳ Joyfulness/enthusiasm/cheerfulness
– I don't know

↳ Optimism/hope
– I don't know

↳ Gratitude/thankfulness
– Yes

↳ Reverence/awe/wonder
– Yes

↳ Faith/belief/trust/devotion
– I don't know

↳ Wisdom/understanding
– Yes

↳ Discernment/intelligence
– Yes

↳ Beauty/attractiveness
– Yes
Notes: This is more evident in the Sumerian version.

↳ Cleanliness (physical)/orderliness
– Yes

↳ Other important virtues
– Yes

Does the text require fasting?

– No

Are there special treatments for adherents' corpses dictated in the text?

– Yes

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- ↳ Cremation?
 - No
- ↳ Mummification?
 - No
- ↳ Interment?
 - No
- ↳ Cannibalism?
 - No
- ↳ Exposure to elements (e.g. air drying)?
 - No
- ↳ Feeding to animals?
 - No
- ↳ Secondary burial?
 - No
- ↳ Re-treatment of corpse?
 - No
- ↳ Are there specific designations for parts of corpses?
 - No
- ↳ Could parts of corpses become transformed into partial bodily relics?
 - No
- ↳ Other intensive (in terms of time or resources expended) treatment of corpse?
 - No

If the text is not explicitly scripture, is it part of another important literary tradition?
– Field doesn't know

Formulating a specifically religious calendar?

– Field doesn't know

Does the text indicate if co-sacrifices should be present in burials?

– No

Does the text require forgone food opportunities (taboos on desired foods)?

– No

Does the text require permanent scarring or painful bodily alterations?

– No

Notes: No, but the related Sumerian narrative does describe bodily lacerations relating to mourning practices.

Does the text specify grave goods for burial?

– No

Are formal burials present in the text?

– No

Does the text require painful physical positions or transitory painful wounds?

– No

Notes: No, but these are described in the related Sumerian narrative.

Does the text require sacrifice of adults?

– No

Notes: No, but there is the sacrifice of Ishtar's husband to take her place in the Underworld.

Are there practices that have funerary associations presented in the text?

– Yes

Do these practices take place at tombs/burial sites?

– No

Do these practices take place for the veneration OR worship of the dead?

– Yes

↳ For the worship of a deceased person(s)?
– No

↳ For the worship of a deified human?
– No

↳ For the worship of a deceased hero?
– No

↳ For the veneration of a deceased person(s)?
– Yes

↳ For the veneration of a deified human?
– No

↳ For the veneration of a deceased hero?
– No

Are supernatural beings present in the text?

– Yes

↳ A supreme high-god is present
– No

Notes: No, but yes in the Sumerian version.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1500 BCE - 1000 BCE

Does the text require sacrifice of children?

– No

Previously human spirits are present

– No

Notes: There are Underworld demons.

Does the text require self-sacrifice (suicide)?

– No

Non-human supernatural beings are present

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings can be seen

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings can be physically felt

– Yes

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have knowledge of this world

– Yes

↳ Knowledge is restricted to a particular domain of human affairs

– I don't know

↳ Knowledge is restricted to (a) specific area(s) within the sample region

– I don't know

↳ Knowledge is unrestricted within the sample region

– I don't know

↳ Knowledge is unrestricted outside of sample region

– I don't know

↳ Can see you everywhere normally visible (in public)

– Yes

↳ Can see you everywhere (in the dark, at home)

– No

↳ Can see inside heart/mind (hidden motives)

– Yes

↳ Know basic character (personal essence)

– Yes

- ↳ Know what will happen to you, what you will do (future sight)
 - I don't know
- ↳ Have other knowledge of this world
 - Yes
- ↳ Non-human supernatural beings have deliberate causal efficacy in the world
 - Yes
- ↳ Supernatural beings can reward
 - Yes
- ↳ Supernatural beings can punish
 - Yes
- ↳ Non-human supernatural beings communicate with the living according to the text?
 - Yes
 - ↳ In waking, everyday life?
 - Yes
 - ↳ In dreams?
 - Yes
 - ↳ In trance possession?
 - Field doesn't know
 - ↳ Through divination practices?
 - Yes
 - ↳ Only through religious specialists?
 - Field doesn't know
 - ↳ Only through monarch?
 - No

↳ Other?

–Specify: Unknown

↳ These supernatural beings have indirect causal efficacy in the world

– Yes

↳ These supernatural beings exhibit positive emotion

– Yes

↳ These supernatural beings exhibit negative emotion

– Yes

↳ These supernatural beings possess hunger

– Yes

↳ These supernatural beings possess/exhibit some other feature

–Specify: Ishtar shows the ability to elevate her status by enhancing her appearance.

Does the text require sacrifice of property/valuable items?

– No

Does the text require sacrifice of time (e.g. attendance at meetings or services, regular prayer, etc.)?

– I don't know

Does the text attest to a pantheon of supernatural beings?

– Yes

↳ Organized by kinship based on a family model?

– Yes

↳ Organized hierarchically?

– Yes

↳ Power of beings is domain specific?

– Yes

Notes: Yes and no. There is a lot of overlap, and much we do not know.

↳ Other organization of pantheon?

–Specify: There is some astral alignment with roles in the pantheon, for example, Ishtar is associated with Venus.

Are mixed human-divine beings present according to the text?

– I don't know

Notes: Not quasi-divine like Gilgamesh, but several beings with anthropomorphic forms but supernatural attributes.

Does the text require physical risk taking?

– No

Notes: No, but it is described in the narrative.

Is there a supernatural being that is physically present in the/as a result of the text?

– I don't know

Does the text require accepting ethical precepts?

– No

Are other categories of beings present?

– Mysterious?

Does the text require marginalization by out-group members?

– No

Does the text guide divination practices?

– Field doesn't know

Does the text require participation in small-scale rituals (private, household)?

– No

Does the text require participation in large-scale rituals?

– No

Are extra-ritual in-group markers present as indicated in the text?

– I don't know

Does the text employ fictive kinship terminology?

– I don't know

Does the text include elements that are intended to be entertaining?

– Yes

↳ Drama?

– Yes

↳ Comedy?

– I don't know

Notes: I think so, but the field probably would not necessarily support this view.

↳ Tragedy?

– Yes

↳ Epic entertainment?

– Yes

Does the text specify sacrifices, offerings, and maintenance of a sacred space?

– No

Context

Is the text itself accompanied by art?

– No

Notes: No, although it has been argued persuasively that the Burney Relief reflects Ishtar in the narrative.

Are there multiple versions of the text?

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Notes: There is an earlier Sumerian version which is longer and more detailed, along with the manuscripts from Ashurbanipal's Library and Assur.

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↳ Is there debate about which version is proper?

– No

Notes: Both versions are considered to reflect variations of the story.

Is the text part of a collection of texts?

– Field doesn't know

Notes: There are related stories, such as the courtship of Inanna and Dumuzi, but it is unclear how it all fits together.

If the text is not explicitly scripture, is it part of another important literary tradition?

– Field doesn't know

Content

Is the text - or does the text include - a ritual list, manual, bibliography, index, or vocabulary?
(Select all that apply)

– Other [specify]: No

Are there lineages or a single lineage established by the text?

– No

Does the text express a formal legal code?

– No

Formulating a specifically religious calendar?

– Field doesn't know

Beliefs

Is a spirit-body distinction present in the text?

– I don't know

Is belief in an afterlife indicated in the text?

– Yes

↳ Is the spatial location of the afterlife specified or described by the religious group?
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↳ Afterlife in specified realm of space beyond this world?
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↳ Afterlife in vaguely defined "above" space?
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↳ Is the temporality of the afterlife specified or described by the religious group?
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↳ Is there debate in the interpretation of the language of the afterlife?
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↳ What are the historically mainstream positions in the debate?

–Specify: There is some debate about where the entrance to the Underworld may be located

↳ What are the historically minority positions?

–Specify: See above debate on entrance to the Underworld.

Is belief in reincarnation in this world specified in the text?

– Yes

↳ In human form?

– No

↳ In animal/plant form?

– No

↳ In form of an inanimate object(s)?

– No

↳ In non-individual form (i.e. some form of corporate rebirth, tribe, lineage, etc.)?

– No

↳ Reincarnation linked to notion of life-transcending causality (e.g. karma)?

– Yes

↳ Other form of reincarnation in this world?

– Yes

↳ In textual exegesis among practitioners are there debates about reincarnation?

– No

Are there special treatments for adherents' corpses dictated in the text?

– Yes

↳ Cremation?

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↳ Mummification?

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↳ Interment?

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Are there practices that have funerary associations presented in the text?

– Yes

↳ Do these practices take place at tombs/burial sites?

– No

↳ Do these practices take place for the veneration OR worship of the dead?

– Yes

↳ For the worship of a deceased person(s)?

– No

↳ For the worship of a deified human?

– No

↳ For the worship of a deceased hero?

– No

↳ For the veneration of a deceased person(s)?

– Yes

↳ For the veneration of a deified human?

– No

↳ For the veneration of a deceased hero?

– No

Are supernatural beings present in the text?

– Yes

↳ A supreme high-god is present

– No

Notes: No, but yes in the Sumerian version.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1500 BCE - 1000 BCE

Previously human spirits are present

– No

Notes: There are Underworld demons.

Non-human supernatural beings are present

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings can be seen

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings can be physically felt

– Yes

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have knowledge of this world

– Yes

↳ Knowledge is restricted to a particular domain of human affairs

– I don't know

↳ Knowledge is restricted to (a) specific area(s) within the sample region

– I don't know

↳ Knowledge is unrestricted within the sample region

– I don't know

↳ Knowledge is unrestricted outside of sample region

– I don't know

↳ Can see you everywhere normally visible (in public)

– Yes

↳ Can see you everywhere (in the dark, at home)

– No

- ↳ Can see inside heart/mind (hidden motives)
 - Yes
- ↳ Know basic character (personal essence)
 - Yes
- ↳ Know what will happen to you, what you will do (future sight)
 - I don't know
- ↳ Have other knowledge of this world
 - Yes
- ↳ Non-human supernatural beings have deliberate causal efficacy in the world
 - Yes
- ↳ Supernatural beings can reward
 - Yes
- ↳ Supernatural beings can punish
 - Yes
- ↳ Non-human supernatural beings communicate with the living according to the text?
 - Yes
- ↳ In waking, everyday life?
 - Yes
- ↳ In dreams?
 - Yes
- ↳ In trance possession?
 - Field doesn't know
- ↳ Through divination practices?
 - Yes

↳ Only through religious specialists?

– Field doesn't know

↳ Only through monarch?

– No

↳ Other?

–Specify: Unknown

↳ These supernatural beings have indirect causal efficacy in the world

– Yes

↳ These supernatural beings exhibit positive emotion

– Yes

↳ These supernatural beings exhibit negative emotion

– Yes

↳ These supernatural beings possess hunger

– Yes

↳ These supernatural beings possess/exhibit some other feature

–Specify: Ishtar shows the ability to elevate her status by enhancing her appearance.

Does the text attest to a pantheon of supernatural beings?

– Yes

↳ Organized by kinship based on a family model?

– Yes

↳ Organized hierarchically?

– Yes

↳ Power of beings is domain specific?

– Yes

Notes: Yes and no. There is a lot of overlap, and much we do not know.

↳ Other organization of pantheon?

– Specify: There is some astral alignment with roles in the pantheon, for example, Ishtar is associated with Venus.

Are mixed human-divine beings present according to the text?

– I don't know

Notes: Not quasi-divine like Gilgamesh, but several beings with anthropomorphic forms but supernatural attributes.

Is there a supernatural being that is physically present in the/as a result of the text?

– I don't know

Are other categories of beings present?

– Mysterious?

Does the text guide divination practices?

– Field doesn't know

Supernatural Monitoring

Is supernatural monitoring present in the text?

– No

Do supernatural beings mete out punishment in the text?

– No

Notes: Yes but not to humans

Do supernatural beings bestow rewards in the text?

– No

Notes: Yes but not to humans. Ishtar rewards her faithful followers in the Sumerian version.

Messianism/Eschatology

Are messianic beliefs present in the text?

– No

Is an eschatology present in the text?

– No

Norms & Moral Realism

Are general social norms prescribed by the text?

– Yes

Is there a conventional vs. moral distinction in the religious text?

– No

Are there centrally important virtues advocated by the text?

– Yes

↳ Honesty/trustworthiness/integrity

– Yes

↳ Courage (in battle)

– No

↳ Courage (generic)

– Yes

↳ Compassion/empathy/kindness/benevolence

– Yes

↳ Mercy/forgiveness/tolerance

– Yes

↳ Generosity/charity

– No

↳ Selflessness/selfless giving

– Yes

↳ Righteousness/moral rectitude

– Yes

↳ Ritual purity/ritual adherence/abstention from sources of impurity

– Yes

↳ Respectfulness/courtesy

– Yes

↳ Familial obedience/filial piety

– Yes

↳ Fidelity/loyalty

– Yes

Notes: Big yes.

↳ Cooperation

– Yes

↳ Independence/creativity/freedom

– Yes

↳ Moderation/frugality

– No

↳ Forbearance/fortitude/patience

– No

↳ Diligence/self-discipline/excellence

– Yes

↳ Assertiveness/decisiveness/confidence/initiative

– Yes

↳ Strength (physical)

– No

↳ Power/status/nobility

– Yes

- ↳ Humility/modesty
 - Yes
- ↳ Contentment/serenity/equanimity
 - No
- ↳ Joyfulness/enthusiasm/cheerfulness
 - I don't know
- ↳ Optimism/hope
 - I don't know
- ↳ Gratitude/thankfulness
 - Yes
- ↳ Reverence/awe/wonder
 - Yes
- ↳ Faith/belief/trust/devotion
 - I don't know
- ↳ Wisdom/understanding
 - Yes
- ↳ Discernment/intelligence
 - Yes
- ↳ Beauty/attractiveness
 - Yes
 - Notes: This is more evident in the Sumerian version.
- ↳ Cleanliness (physical)/orderliness
 - Yes
- ↳ Other important virtues
 - Yes

Advocacy of Practices

Does the text require celibacy (full sexual abstinence)?

– No

Does the text require constraints on sexual activity (partial sexual abstinence)?

– No

Notes: No, but Ishtar's death results in the temporary cessation of all earthly fertility, causing a cosmic crisis.

Does the text require castration?

– No

Does the text require fasting?

– No

Does the text require forgone food opportunities (taboos on desired foods)?

– No

Does the text require permanent scarring or painful bodily alterations?

– No

Notes: No, but the related Sumerian narrative does describe bodily lacerations relating to mourning practices.

Does the text require painful physical positions or transitory painful wounds?

– No

Notes: No, but these are described in the related Sumerian narrative.

Does the text require sacrifice of adults?

– No

Notes: No, but there is the sacrifice of Ishtar's husband to take her place in the Underworld.

Does the text require sacrifice of children?

– No

Does the text require self-sacrifice (suicide)?

– No

Does the text require sacrifice of property/valuable items?

– No

Does the text require sacrifice of time (e.g. attendance at meetings or services, regular prayer, etc.)?

– I don't know

Does the text require physical risk taking?

– No

Notes: No, but it is described in the narrative.

Does the text require accepting ethical precepts?

– No

Does the text require marginalization by out-group members?

– No

Does the text require participation in small-scale rituals (private, household)?

– No

Does the text require participation in large-scale rituals?

– No

Are extra-ritual in-group markers present as indicated in the text?

– I don't know

Does the text employ fictive kinship terminology?

– I don't know

Does the text include elements that are intended to be entertaining?

– Yes

↳ Drama?

– Yes

↳ Comedy?

– I don't know

Notes: I think so, but the field probably would not necessarily support this view.

↳ Tragedy?

– Yes

↳ Epic entertainment?

– Yes

Does the text specify sacrifices, offerings, and maintenance of a sacred space?

– No

Institutions & Production Environment of Text

Is bureaucracy regulated by this text?

– No

Does the text mention warfare?

– No

Society of religious group that produced the text is best characterized as:

– An empire

Does the text specify forms of taxation?

– No

Does the text detail interaction with public works?

– No

Does the text mentioned food production/disbursement?

– No

Are there formal educational institutions available for teaching the text?

– Yes

Does the text specify institutionalized famine relief?

– No

Does the text specify institutionalized poverty relief?

– No

Are there specific elements of society that have controlled the reproduction of the text?

– Other

Are there formal educational institutions specified according to the text?

– Field doesn't know

Are there specific elements of society involved with the destruction of the text?

– Other

Does the text specify institutionalized care for elderly & infirm?

– No

Does the text make provisions for non-religious education?

– No

Does the text restrict education to religious professionals?

– Field doesn't know

Other forms of welfare?

– No

Notes: Unless we consider correct mourning practices for the dead a type of welfare.

Does the text restrict education among religious professionals?

– No

Is education gendered according to the text?

– Field doesn't know

Is education gendered with respect to this text and larger textual tradition?

– Field doesn't know

Does the text specify teaching relationships or ratios? (i.e.: 1:20; 1:1)

– No

Are there specific relationships to teachers that are advocated by the text?

– No

Are there worldly rewards/benefits to education according to the text specified by the text itself?

– No

Society & Institutions

Society of religious group that produced the text is best characterized as:

– An empire

Are there specific elements of society that have controlled the reproduction of the text?

– Other

Are there specific elements of society involved with the destruction of the text?

– Other

Welfare

Does the text specify institutionalized famine relief?

– No

Does the text specify institutionalized poverty relief?

– No

Does the text specify institutionalized care for elderly & infirm?

– No

Other forms of welfare?

– No

Notes: Unless we consider correct mourning practices for the dead a type of welfare.

Education

Are there formal educational institutions available for teaching the text?

– Yes

Are there formal educational institutions specified according to the text?

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Does the text make provisions for non-religious education?

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Are there specific relationships to teachers that are advocated by the text?

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Are there worldly rewards/benefits to education according to the text specified by the text itself?

– No

Bureaucracy

Is bureaucracy regulated by this text?

– No

Public Works

Does the text detail interaction with public works?

– No

Taxation

Does the text specify forms of taxation?

– No

Warfare

Does the text mention warfare?

– No

Food Production

Does the text mentioned food production/disbursement?

– No

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